

The Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on the Ability to Recognize Entrepreneurial Opportunities (Case Study: Technical and Vocational Training Centres in Sari City)

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ABSTRACT: The lack of entrepreneurial opportunities in many organizations and individuals has caused the unemployment rate to increase in the country and a significant share in different fields; employment decreases day by day. In this regard, opportunity recognition is one of the critical pillars of entrepreneurship education that has been considered in entrepreneurship studies in recent years. This study aimed to investigate the effect of entrepreneurship education on capability.

Identify entrepreneurial opportunities of individuals and organizations regarding the Sari brothers centre, Sari Sister Centre, Farahabad dual-purpose centre of Sari city was selected from technical and vocational training centres. The measurement tool of this study is a questionnaire, and SPSS software for analysis Data was used. Data were collected by a researcher-made questionnaire containing 31 questionnaires, and its validity was done through four experts. Entrepreneurship and dynamics were confirmed by calculating Cronbach's alpha with a coefficient of 0/8056. This research is calculated through Krejcie and Morgan formulas by 59 people. A sample size of 70 experts and trainers with several years of experience in technical and vocational training centres in Sari City were calculated and studied. Based on the results of this study, entrepreneurship education is effective in identifying entrepreneurial opportunities and Entrepreneurship education in six factors of active search, awareness, prior knowledge, social capital, environmental factors and cognitive and individual characteristics of diagnosis.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurship Education, Identifying Entrepreneurial Opportunities, Trainees, Rehabilitation.

INTRODUCTION

Today, entrepreneurship education is one of the most critical and extensive educational institutions associated with human creation. In other words, entrepreneurship is considered as the centre of gravity of work and human endeavour and progress in the present age. Entrepreneurship, The same process of establishing or developing a business, is based on a new idea. Entrepreneurship needs to exist to grow and develop in societies. It is a unique culture due to the critical importance of entrepreneurship in modern economies (creation of small and medium companies), different countries, and programs that have provided detailed tools for developing such a culture in their community to continue growing and becoming dynamic. Therefore identifying entrepreneurial opportunities and developing entrepreneurship education in society and various economic, cultural, social and political dimensions (Acs et al., 2008). In such a way that the element of entrepreneurship as a driving force of production and economic development and, on the other hand, nurtures and strengthens the spirit of capital investment and productivity in human resources is considered this study to examine the impact of entrepreneurship education on the ability to identify opportunities Entrepreneurial (technical and vocational training centres of Sari city) has been made Statistical community in this study instructors and experts of technical and vocational training centres in Sari city, and the statistical sample was 59 people. The results of the central hypothesis of the research shown that entrepreneurship education is about identifying entrepreneurial opportunities for trainees in training centres. There is a significant technical and professional impact. The research hypotheses showed that the lack of entrepreneurship education Ability to recognize the entrepreneurial opportunities of trainees in technical and vocational training centres negatively affects.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Entrepreneurship, the culture of understanding change and discovering opportunities Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial companies keep pace with change and create opportunities. Discover and exploit these changes. Keeping up with change requires a cultural context that values difference and welcomes it. There is an abandonment of traditional and old approaches and practices and choose new methods. Today, government agencies, such as private NGOs, face how to train and develop entrepreneurship. Today's organizations operate in a dynamic, pragmatic and evolving environment (Teece. 2016).

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The present is a dramatic and continuous change in thinking, social values, ways of doing work and many other phenomena of life. Organizations face changes that in today's world of customer orientation and increasing competition have crushed any resistance and pushed everyone forward. The breadth and variety of change that comes to today's organizations are so great that they have no choice but adapt and respond to these changes (Sisodia, 2003).

It does not exist, so entrepreneurial development plays an essential role in today's turbulent world. There must be reasonable conditions to promote entrepreneurship. Factors that affect the outcome of entrepreneurship is called the entrepreneurial atmosphere. Education plays a crucial role in developing this critical matter (Phan & Siegel, 2006). In this study, the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurship development in technical and vocational training centres of Sari city for development Entrepreneurship culture can be considered.

On the other hand, the influential factors in moving skill training centres towards an entrepreneurial centre are another critical point that should be considered. Although in recent years, with the launch of incubators and technology parks, significant steps have been taken. Technical training centres and professions are far from becoming entrepreneurial centre. The most important question raised in this regard is why graduates of technical and vocational training centres in Iran are not entrepreneurs and how to move the output of skill training centres toward a more significant influence in entrepreneurship (Karimi et al., 2017).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Main objective:

The effect of Entrepreneurship training on Entrepreneurial opportunities recognition (Case Study: Trainees of Sari Vocational Training Centres).

By-objectives:

- 1- Rehabilitation of entrepreneurship opportunity for trainees.
- 2- Rehabilitation of creating entrepreneurial opportunity for trainees.
- 3- Rehabilitation of personal skills of trainees.
- 4- Rehabilitation of environmental factors in trainees.
- 5- Rehabilitation of understanding the needs and problems of society for trainees.

THE IMPORTANCE AND NECESSITY OF THE RESEARCH SUBJECT

It is now increasingly expected that technical and vocational training centres and scientific and practical education should also perform another task. Each region's initiatives and economic growth are undertaken to achieve economic growth and respond to the most significant challenges; Financial, i.e. improving living standards, employment and increasing tax revenues, are operating (Chatterton & Goddard, 2000). Investment Policies Education of governments (generally training and partially skill training) tied to national objectives. These educational policies can be inappropriate circumstances and cause definite advantages for countries. In the meantime, professionalism has long been of interest to the public. Acquiring expertise and skills as a valuable and profitable experience, while employable and income-generating, is a subject whose necessities have never been undue from prosperity and importance (Stiglitz & Greenwald, 2014).

A significant part of the country's active population does not have sufficient skills and expertise to do the current situation. Some of the employees do not have job competence or, to be more precise and standardized. In the labour market, professions and skills in expertise and technical reserves are not desirable and efficient. Technical and vocational education, an independent organization called the Technical and Vocational Education Organization of the country, provides all kinds of training, service, technical, etc., which has an influential role in designing and implementing training courses and offers desirable services to applicants and art seekers. Technical and vocational education is a practical and scientific education that aims to create the necessary conditions for acquiring knowledge and developing attitudes and upbringing (Barrett et al., 2014).

The trainees' skills are getting a job and improving their skills and leading to receiving a certificate. These training courses are in the form of 2 to 24 months with training in fixed centres, on-the-job training, coach training, and training in free schools. Through this, the supply and training of staff skilled required by various industrial sectors of agriculture and services of the country. Currently, the primary orientation of technical and vocational education, hardware skills training (transfer of equipment and profession to equipment) to trainees are expected to complete training courses with the considerable cost of the public (Bass & Avolio, 1990). The private sector is implemented to build a shop such as a car repair shop to create jobs for oneself and others. Nothing Provide software skills training related to marketing innovation and creativity, how to formulate and evaluate a business plan, market study, business finance methods work, wealth creation and value creation, which is entrepreneurship, are among the limitations and issues that significantly affect the effectiveness of technical and vocational training has changed the attitude of technical and vocational training centres from technical to entrepreneurial activity can improve the effectiveness of training Be technical and skilled and direct these training from wage employment to self-employment and identifying entrepreneurial opportunities (Chen et al., 1998). And this shortcoming can be seen in technical and vocational training centres of Sari city.

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The main question of the research

Does entrepreneurship education affect the recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities?

- 1- Does entrepreneurship education affect the education of seeking the entrepreneurial opportunity of trainees?
- 2- Does entrepreneurship education affect the rehabilitation of creating the chance of trainees?
- 3- Does entrepreneurship education affect the educable of recognizing the personal skills of entrepreneurship trainees?
- 4- Does entrepreneurship education affect the improvement of environmental factors of entrepreneurship of trainees?
- 5- Does entrepreneurship education affect the understanding of the needs and problems of entrepreneurship of trainees

The central hypothesis of the research

Entrepreneurship education affects the ability to recognize entrepreneurial opportunities.

The assumptions of the research:

- 1- Entrepreneurship training affects the seeking the entrepreneurial opportunity of trainees?
- 2- Entrepreneurship training affects the rehabilitation of creating the opportunity for trainees?
- 3- Entrepreneurship training effects of recognizing the personal skills of entrepreneurship trainees?
- 4- Entrepreneurship training impacts the edict of recognizing the environmental factors of entrepreneurship of trainees?
- 5- Entrepreneurship training affects the understanding of the needs and problems of the entrepreneurship of trainees?

Definitions of research principles and variables:

Purpose of the entrepreneur:

Different definitions have been expressed in Persian and foreign sources for the entrepreneur, which the researcher mention.

An entrepreneur is a factor that all tools combine production and takes responsibility for the value of the products, recycling the entire capital it employs, the value of the wages, interest and rent it pays, and profits (Bacq & Janssen, 2011).

The entrepreneur is the main driving force in economic development, and his role is to innovate or create new combinations of materials (Akbari & Baharestan, 2013).

Entrepreneurs as an Accelerator, Spark Growth and Economic Development (Radojevich-Kelley & Hoffman, 2012).

An entrepreneur starts a new small business with his capital (Bridge & O'Neill, 2012).

Entrepreneurs are people who innovate, identify business opportunities, create new combinations of resources rather than in the absence of definitely benefit from these innovations (Bacq & Janssen, 2011).

According to Kayed and Hassan (2013), an entrepreneur is united to organize, manage, and assume the risks of economic activity. According to Islam, an entrepreneur is a person who strives to be able to rely on God and rely on God to the maximum of his physical, material and professional abilities in society.

The concept of the word entrepreneurship

The word "entrepreneurship" is derived from the French word *Entreprendre*, meaning to commit.

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a process or concept in which the entrepreneur comes up with new and creative ideas and identifies new opportunities with recent mobilizations, new organizations and a growing innovator. This goes hand in hand with accepting the risks of resources by creating businesses. Therefore, "entrepreneurs" are agents of change. That is, they often lead to the introduction of a product or service to the community, sometimes leading to astonishing progress. Entrepreneurship is the process of changing and creating something different. A new economic identity based on a novel product or service, or at the very least, on something significantly different from the products or services offered anywhere else in the market (Davila et al., 2009).

Entrepreneurship education

According to a comprehensive definition, education means information and intellectual development obtained through formal and informal education. Basis Education is about learning, and every organization strives to help people perform well in their jobs. The training program is the same as organizing this experience to adapt and improve the attitudes or skills needed. Therefore, organizations' effort to change people behave through the learning process and increase their effectiveness (Eshach, 2007).

Entrepreneurial opportunity

The mission of entrepreneurial research is the continuous and systematic search for factors that affect the ability of individuals to seek and create opportunities. Research achievements can be used in the design of entrepreneurship training courses. Because according to the above conclusion, the primary purpose of entrepreneurship education is nothing but to empower people to seek and create opportunities (Hackett & Dilts, 2004).

RESEARCH ANALYTICAL MODEL

In this study, the researcher intends to examine the role of entrepreneurship education in entrepreneurship development. For this purpose, as a set of training agents, the researcher defines variables and examines their entrepreneurial development impact.

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Depending on what is needed, to justify the effect of attribute cultivation variables (control centre, pragmatism, salutation) calmness, intellectual, ambiguity tolerance, Dreaming, Challenge, Opportunity Recognition, Entrepreneurial Consciousness (Motivation), Desire for Wealth, need for Success, Independence, Willingness to Create new things, entrepreneurial intent, creating value for society, not accepting existing methods (and entrepreneurial knowledge and skills) work ability in a team having communication skills, ability to study financial issues and resource acquisition, familiarity with management principles, familiarity with economic matters, ability to discover new ways in carrying out activities, having a competitive ability and maintaining a position in the market, being able to find new markets to increase the provision of goods and services at the national and international level, Internal control, risk-taking, innovation, ability to manage change, change-oriented, perseverance, far-sighted leadership, planning and goal setting, decision making, Human Relations, Marketing, Starting a Business, Negotiation, Writing Skills, Oral or Verbal Communication, Environmental Monitoring or Evaluation, Business Management, Work, Interpersonal Skills, Listening Skills, Organizational Ability, Participatory Management, Coaching, Coaching, Team Role Playing (on Development Entrepreneurship presented).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is applied for this purpose because it has been used to solve real and executive problems in the descriptive survey method. A survey is a method in which information is collected through people who are called accountable and answer questions.

Community and sample size of research

The statistical population also called the statistical population, is a set of individuals with common characteristics that are researched. The critical task of the researcher is to define society wholly and accurately. The definition of society must be precisely the elements that belong to society. In this study, the statistical population of all instructors and experts of technical and vocational training centres in Sari is 70 people. The sample size is several people in the community whose traits are similar to the characteristics of the community and are known to the community, while the district is homogeneous. (Bartlett, 1957).

Information Collection Tools

Information can be collected in a variety of ways in different places and from a variety of sources. Information gathering methods including a face-to-face interview, Telephone interview, computer interview, face-to-face, postal or electronic questionnaire, observation of people or events with or without audio or video recording, and other techniques motivation such as projection tests and information sources can be first or second hand or both. In this research, the researcher collecting questionnaire information, dissertation books, articles, the internet, etc. They collect data by reading and exploring articles, books and dissertations, and another part of a questionnaire.

Investigating research assumptions

The central hypothesis of the research

H0: The average score given to the impact of entrepreneurship education on seeking entrepreneurial opportunity is smaller or equal to 3.

H1: The average score given to the impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurship development is greater than 3.

H1 : $\mu > 3$

H0 : $\mu \leq 3$

Table 1. Net statistical results related to the central hypothesis of the research

Average standard error	Standard deviation	Average	Number of communities	Index
.625	.64277	4.1295	59	Main hypotheses
.06749	.51844	4.2136	59	Sub-hypotheses1
.06957	.51702	4.0367	59	Sub-hypotheses2
.06731	.53436	4.1220	59	Sub-hypotheses3
.06956	.53426	4.1130	59	Sub-hypotheses4
.06701	.51471	4.1622	59	Sub-hypotheses5

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Table 1 shows average, standard deviation and means error. The results of the descriptive statistics test show that the average value of the sample is greater than or less than 3. Still, this subject must be confirmed through inferential statistics (assumption test or uncertainty interval).

Table 2. Results of t-Test sample indicators of the central hypothesis of the research

Test value=3						Index
95% confidence interval.		The average difference.	(sig)	Degree of Freedom	T	
Up	Low					
1.2501	1.0089	1.12951	.000	58	18.748	Main hypotheses
1.3487	1.785	1.21356	.000	58	17.980	Sub-hypotheses1
1.1715	.9020	1.03672	.000	58	15.402	Sub-hypotheses2
1.2613	.9828	1.2203	.000	58	16.129	Sub-hypotheses3
1.2522	.9738	1.11299	.000	58	16.002	Sub-hypotheses4
1.2964	1.0281	1.16223	.000	58	17.344	Sub-hypotheses5

The verdict of the central hypothesis is defined as that according to the questionnaire and the spectrum of responses, the average of opinions is equal to or less than 3. Assumption of the opposite is either a hypothesis according to the questionnaire, and the range of answers, the mean of the comments is more than 3. As shown in the table above, the level of 95% confidence (or Error 5%) of the up limit is positive, and the lower limit is positive. The observed error rate is (0.000), which is less than 0/05, so assume H1 Confirmation and assumption H0 ignored. That is, training entrepreneurship skills have an impact on entrepreneurship development.

Friedman's ranking is used to prioritize the factors affecting the entrepreneurship development of trainees, the results of which are as follows:

Table 3 of the Friedman Test

Acquire skills Entrepreneurial management.	Acquire skills Someone's an entrepreneur	Acquire skills Technically entrepreneurial	Special breeding Entrepreneurship	Entrepreneurship creation	Variables
2.93	3.03	3.16	2.41	3.47	Average ranking

According to the average results, it can be said that creating entrepreneurial incentives with an average of 3.47 has the highest rank and nurturing characteristics and Entrepreneurship with an average of 2.41 has the lowest level.

Suggestion

Research Proposals for Technical and Vocational Training Centres

1- According to the results of the first hypothesis that the positive relationship between identifying entrepreneurship opportunities of trainees based on opportunity search rehabilitation through entrepreneurship training, there are trainees in technical and vocational training centres, so it is recommended to the managers of the centres that in addition to training skills (hardware) definitely software training (Entrepreneurship) which includes wealth training, the need for success, independence, the desire to create things new, entrepreneurial intent and value creation for the community as a separate educational standard or a combination of standard words as part of the training program for trainees Centers that promote and make the skills training of the centres more effective.

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2- Considering the second hypothesis results, which showed a positive relationship between creating entrepreneurial opportunities for trainees and entrepreneurship education. Therefore, it is suggested to the centres' managers that in addition to skill training (hardware) in software and vocational training centres, software training must be provided. Entrepreneurship (which includes self-confidence, self-confidence, opportunity recognition, the ability to tolerate ambiguity, dreaming, pragmatism, and peace of mind to promote and increase the centres' training's effectiveness should be considered.

3- The third hypothesis results showed a positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and recognizing personal entrepreneurial skills. Therefore, it is suggested that the managers of technical and vocational training centres and the necessary skills training (hardware) of any profession, software training. Trainees should be trained in risk-taking, managing change, innovation, change-oriented, leadership resistance and foresight.

4- The fourth hypothesis results showed a positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and understanding of entrepreneurial environmental factors. It is recommended that the managers of technical and vocational training centres and the necessary skills training (hardware) in each profession include software training included in the program. Goal setting, decision making, human relations, marketing, business start-up, financial and accounting skills, management, control, negotiation for success and trainee management should be trained to provide more entrepreneurship.

5. The fifth hypothesis results showed a positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and understanding of entrepreneurial needs and problems. It is recommended that managers of technical and vocational training centres in addition to skills training (hardware) required for any profession, software training (entrepreneurship), writing skills, oral and verbal communication, environmental monitoring, business management, technology, interpersonal skills, listening skills, ability organize and manage the participation of the trainees to create more commitment and entrepreneurship for the trainees.

Side suggestions for technical and vocational training centres

The fact is that as in answer to question one, the questionnaire to what extent entrepreneurship education has been considered in technical and vocational education centres, more than 90% answered poorly and very poorly, meaning that one of the challenges of today's technological and vocational training centres is entrepreneurship training, and implementing a successful and practical entrepreneurship education program requires considering all aspects of entrepreneurship. But whether there are technical and vocational training centres, all these facilities and equipment and intellectual flow spent only on skills training (without entrepreneurship training) can implement such a program or No, it is not clear. Care should be taken to fully integrate the hardware and software training (entrepreneurship) in technical and vocational training centres. Ultimately, it has been studied and combined so that it has the necessary and expected effects. Only providing hardware skills training, even with quality excellent without software skills training (entrepreneurship), will not be suitable, and despite the high cost of hardware skills training in technical training centres and professional will cause misguidance and deviation from the path of the goals of the Technical and Vocational Education Organization, which is the same as production-oriented training, so it should be by studying the environment around technical and vocational training centres and the setting of entrepreneurial business and taking into account the existing capabilities and possibilities, a long-term and comprehensive program was designed and implemented. Entrepreneurship education is at several levels, which includes the necessary field of direction. The development of software skills (entrepreneurship) trainees will impact this, in general, an approach to integrating entrepreneurship training in the system. Skills training means integrating entrepreneurship training standard as part of any training profession's hardware training standard.

1. Combining vocational training standards with entrepreneurship training is software training (entrepreneurship) as part of the standard of educational professions.

2. According to the research findings, it is necessary for the trainees' training programs to develop the trainees' software skills (entrepreneurship) under review.

3. When preparing and compiling the annual training commitment of technical and vocational training centres for training applicants, needs assessment is the first step to identify the gap to show between the current situation and the desired training courses based on learning the entrepreneurial skills of the trainees.

4. Based on the research results, it is suggested that the letter should be considered to develop the trainees' entrepreneurial skills when designing educational standards. For this purpose, it is possible to integrate entrepreneurship education as part of the professional education standard or provide an independent entrepreneurship course as a supplementary course that should be considered for all trainees.

5. All training courses for trainees to develop characteristics, motivate and developing software skills (entrepreneurship) trainees should promote and the development of knowledge, attitude and skills required to be a suitable field in trainees and also, the field of developing mental skills, entrepreneurial spirit, increase entrepreneurial knowledge and training of entrepreneurial trainees.

6. Holding entrepreneurship festivals from kindergarten to high school. Therefore, in addition to developing and expanding the entrepreneurial research approach in private and government institutions such as Ministries of Commerce, Ministry of Cooperatives, it is necessary and social welfare, financial support and information from entrepreneurs, ensuring their economic and social security

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and strengthening professional systems and expanding jobs to be in charge of the Technical and Vocational Education Organization, despite the design of training courses for entrepreneurs, orientation in developed countries Targeting towards entrepreneurship starts from the very beginning and in all educational levels, it is tried to motivate and motivate students to Entrepreneurship should be strengthened. Still, given the current state of society, entrepreneurship courses in institutions' programs should be courses. Even military training should train instructors and professors of entrepreneurship education by holding specialized conferences and educational activities. The research examines entrepreneurship from an economic, sociological and psychological perspective and provides a suitable web for identifying and growing entrepreneurs.

7. Based on the experiences of the past 15 years, it is suggested that researchers in technical and vocational training centres turn a technical and vocational training centre into a centre. To be an entrepreneur and create wealth, the manager or head of the centre or region must be an entrepreneur because not every manager can be an entrepreneur. Still, every entrepreneur can also be a manager. In other words, it includes hardware and software skills, which software is the same as entrepreneurship.

Suggestions for the next researcher

1. A standard criterion for ranking technical and vocational training centres in the country based on the activities of entrepreneurs in the present study based on the opinions and views of educators and experts of technical and vocational training centres of Sari city regarding entrepreneurship education and activities related to this type of centres have been done. It seems to study the views and opinions of trainees about entrepreneurship education, which is the target community in the country's technical and vocational education organization and all to try the informal skill education system of the government to improve their capabilities.

2. Considering that in the present study, the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurship development in technical and vocational training centres of Sari city. It has been discussed as one of the active centres of Mazandaran province and the country. It is suggested that it be paid in other centres of technical and vocational education of the country as well.

3. It is suggested about the effect of entrepreneurship literacy of managers and heads of technical and vocational training centres on entrepreneurship of technical and vocational training centres can be considered that it can play an essential role in increasing and generating income for the country's technical and vocational education organization and creating employment for trainees after graduation.

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